

NUMERICAL MODELING OF FIBER BUNDLE ARCHITECTURE IN THE ROBOTIC CORELESS FILAMENT WINDING PROCESS

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Keywords: Computational modeling, Finite element analysis FEA, Filament winding

ABSTRACT

The coreless filament winding (CFW) is a novel robot assisted manufacturing process, where impregnated fiber bundles are wound around sleeves in a defined chronological order. Unlike conventional winding, there is no mandrel available to define the resulting shape. Instead the fiber-fiber and fiber-sleeve interaction, influenced by winding sequence and prestress, is forming the final fiber architecture. Depending on the load case of the subsequent area of application, a precise knowledge on the cross-section of the resulting fiber structure is required for a reliable structural evaluation. In order to enable virtual modeling of the forming process, an expansion-based multifilament method is presented. The values for influencing parameters, such as filament diameter, static coefficient of friction, Young's modulus, pretension and penalty stiffness require a balanced interaction and therefore need to be optimised to experimental results during an optimization loop. To evaluate the deviation between simulation results and experimental data, the area and maximal dimensions in a cross-section of a specimen is used.

1 INTRODUCTION

The coreless filament winding technique is a novel robot assisted manufacturing process, where pre-impregnated tows are wound around sleeves in a predefined pattern without a mould resulting in shell-like truss or lattice structures. The flexibility in shape design and its potential for lightweight construction make the process suitable not only for the architectural sector, but also as topology-optimized fiber-reinforced connecting elements or satellite structures. For this highly interconnected structure a sufficient fiber-fiber interaction is required to ensure a reduced buckling length for each free-spanning fiber segment between two fiber connection points [1]. The non-cured, impregnated fibers exhibit no bending resistance during fabrication so that each newly added fiber segment deforms the previous ones [2]. This deformation significantly influences the final shape of the structure and introduces tension in the previously wound fibers. The final structural architecture thus results from fiber-fiber and fiber-sleeve-interaction during the process as well as sleeve point positioning and orientation [3]. A precise cross-section is required to reduce over-dimensioning and material waste. Due to compaction of the fibers during the process and the typically large number of tow crossing points in coreless wound structures, analytical calculation of fiber architecture and bundle cross-sections of

complex structures is challenging. To obtain detailed data prior to fabrication and virtually replicate manufacturing as basis for structural and process optimization, a process simulation workflow has been developed by Hügle et al. using an explicit finite element approach [4]. The finite element approach is able to capture the elastic deformation and friction but requires a long computation time, thus limiting the applicability for large structures. Furthermore, it indicates that modeling of fiber deformation must be included in the simulation for a realistic prediction of fiber architecture and cross-sections. Modeling of a realistic tow shape is a wide-ranging research topic during the generation of unit cell models in woven composite simulation. Here, single and multifilament relaxation models have been used to simulate the fiber-fiber-interaction that form the resulting structure on a sub mesoscale model as reviewed by Wielhorski et al [5]. The approach has been continued by Jones [6] to model the influence of winding sequence and pin configuration on a mandrel for a wound truss structure. In this work the multifilament approach is extended to predict the fiber architecture and cross-sectional yarn deformation of a coreless-wound structure. As a mandrel is not used for this manufacturing technology, an expansion-based approach is applied, which requires a parameter fitting to experimental data to obtain information on realistic fiber bundle deformation.

2 METHODOLOGY

In the following section the fundamentals for the methodology of the simulation approach will be explained. Afterwards the implemented procedure to evaluate selected cross-sections of a simulation result and quantify the deviation to experimental results are described. The methods are then implemented in an optimization loop with the software tool LS-Opt to identify values for the following parameters: virtual fiber diameter, static coefficient of friction, Young's modulus, internal loading and penalty stiffness.

2.1 MODELING APPROACH

The software used for the expansive modeling approach is the solver SimTex, developed by the Bristol Composites Institute. This explicit finite element solver was originally created for digital element simulation with an implementation of fast contact algorithms to reduce computation time for textile forming processes. The digital element method uses chains of artificial beam elements with a reduced stiffness matrix that are connected with joints [7]. This enables a reduced computational effort under usage of non-physically related material data. During multifilament textile forming processes, an initial single tow and respective fiber path, that represents an initial geometry of the fiber architecture, is transferred into arrays of multiple virtual fibers that interact with each other to form the deformed tow shape. This multifilament cross-section is derived by a division of the single virtual filament of the initial fiber path into multiple virtual filaments with a smaller diameter. By varying the number n_{virt_fibers} of virtual fibers per tow that represent it in the simulation and the diameter of this fibers d_{virt_fibers} , a realistic virtual textile architecture and cross-sectional shape can be modelled.

In the modeling approach, a single virtual filament fiber path out of a process simulation by Hügle et al. is transferred in an overlapping multi-filament cross-section (Fig. 1 a)) by scaling of the tow cross-section. In Fig. 1 c) a comparison of different amounts of virtual fibers for a circular virtual tow is displayed, where a single virtual fiber represents several physical fibers. This virtual tow is subsequently expanding due to penalty stiffness in the contact among the individual overlapping virtual filaments (Fig. 1 b)). The initial contact space between the filaments is defined by the dimensions of the mesoscopic fiber path out of the process simulation, where the initial dimension needs to be larger than the scaled virtual tow cross-section, but not too large to enable a sufficient interaction of the virtual filaments. To address this issue an additional internal loading and thus axial shrinking of the elements is applied to control the expansion and fiber interaction in SimTex. This expanding approach enables modeling of large cross-sectional deformations as they occur at intersections of fibers or at sleeves as shown in Fig. 3.

In the virtual filament approach by Jones, the diameter of the virtual filaments is dimensioned to preserve the total area of all physical fibers. The resulting calculated cross-section is then scaled to enable an expansion of the virtual tow. The methodology is also part of a pre-processor for SimTex. As the coreless winding uses pre-impregnated fiber bundles, this approach is extended to preserve the

theoretical wet yarn cross-section A_{wet} for a defined fiber volume ratio FVR , presuming that the total area of the real roving (including resin and neglecting pores) corresponds to the total area of the virtual roving.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of the simulation approach: Initial overlapping virtual filaments (a) of a virtual tow that expand due to contact forces among the filaments controlled by additional internal contraction loading to a final expanded stage (b). Cross section of a circular virtual tow consisting of an increased number of virtual fibers and their respective centroid points (c).

Assuming a complete expansion of the virtual fiber bundle, the required diameter d_{virt_fibers} of a virtual filament in the impregnated modeling approach can be calculated by additional scaling. As the sum of cross-sectional areas of the finite number of virtual elements A_{virt_fibers} is not able to fill the circular cross-sectional wet tow area A_{wet} without free space, the packing density p_d of the virtual fiber bundle needs to be considered. the following equation (Eq. 1) must be satisfied:

$$A_{virt_Fil} = p_d \cdot A_{wet} \quad (1)$$

The value of the fiber volume ratio (FVR) of the wet tow can be calculated according to Eq. 2 using the physical diameter d_{fiber} and number of filaments n_{fibers} :

$$A_{wet} = \frac{n_{fibers} \cdot \pi \cdot \left(\frac{d_{fiber}}{2}\right)^2}{FVR} \quad (2)$$

Considering a FVR of one, the same formula applies for A_{virt_Fil} and thus the diameter of a virtual filament d_{virt_fibers} can be calculated:

$$d_{virt_fibers} = d_{fibers} \sqrt{\frac{p_d \cdot n_{fibers}}{n_{virt_fibers} \cdot FVR}} \quad (3)$$

As shown in Fig. 2, the packing density of the cross-section can change during usage of different numbers of virtual filaments. The packing density of a centroid configuration can be calculated by dividing the total area of all virtual fibers by the resulting diameter d_{virt_tow} of the resulting virtual tow during a pre-calculation with $p_d = 1$ according to Eq. 4.

$$p_d = \frac{n_{virt_fibers} \cdot d_{virt_fibers}^2}{d_{virt_tow}^2} \quad (4)$$

The resulting unscaled cross-section of a virtual tow with 48 virtual fibers and the respective theoretical diameter of the impregnated wet yarn cross-section for the experimental data used in this study with a radius of 1.704 mm is shown in Fig. 3 a). A scaling factor of 0.5 enables a reasonable fiber interaction during expansion and usage of the process simulation results with a bundle thickness of 2.5 mm thickness without overlapping of individual fiber layers resulting in intertwined virtual fibers. A scaled

cross-section with a target scale factor of 0.5 and a resulting radius of 0.961 mm is illustrated in Fig. 3 b). The actual scale factor for this input data is 0.564 as the scaling is applied to the centroids of the fibers neglecting the influence of fiber bundle dimensions.

Figure 2: a) Unscaled cross-section of a virtual tow with 48 virtual fibers and the respective theoretical wet yarn cross-section. B) Scaled virtual tow with a target scale factor of 0.5.

In Fig. 3 shows a simulation model for the analyzed structure and the result after an interaction of the multiple fibers (Fig. 3 b)). The model of the sleeve (detail in Fig. 3 a)) is discretized with triangular *Tri*-elements, that are only used as rigid contact surface and are fixed in their translational and rotational degrees of freedom. The virtual fiber elements are modeled in SimTex as spherocylindrical *Line*-elements. These are defined by a discretization of the initial fiber path into elements of a user defined length. A high amount of virtual fibers with a resulting small diameter will result in a large aspect ratio (element length over diameter) and may cause penetrations at contact areas with a high curvature. To prevent these penetrations, the user-defined length is reduced when setting up the model to ensure an aspect ratio of 4 according to empirical results from Jones. The ends of the fiber path are fixed in fiber direction, but free to move in the cross-sectional plane perpendicular to it, allowing the filaments to move freely in crossing areas or at contact areas with anchors. The end of the yarn must be positioned so that the fibers are pulled towards the sleeve under tensile load. To define this boundary condition, a local coordinate system at each end point is used. As this local coordinate system is depending on fiber path and its discretization, the adjoining elements are used to define the new local x-axis with its direction pointing outward. The new local y-axis is defined with a rotation of the global coordinate system using the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization method and the z-axis as a cross-product of these two axis vectors.

Figure 3: a) Initial configuration of the overlapping virtual fibers with a fiber path extracted out of a previous simulation of the winding process. The detail shows the discretization of the sleeve model. b) SimTex simulation result after interaction of the virtual fibers with each other.

2.2 APPROACH FOR GEOMETRIC ANALYSIS

To enable a comparison of the simulation results with experimental data, a fast but representative approach for the geometrical evaluation of a cross-sectional shape out of a point cloud is required. A convex hull is not sufficient for the irregular convex and non-convex shaped cross-section of those structures. Green et al [8] used a modified version of the convex hull with a finite search radius for a yarn cross-section, showing good agreement with a curved yarn cross-section. The approach is controlled by the local search radius during the construction of a polygon line. A varying average point distance in the data set is disadvantageous and requires an iterative increasing of the search length if no point is found. The same might apply for an alpha-shape, the generalization of a convex hull that calculates the boundary of a point cloud by removing edges from an initial Delaunay triangulation based on an alpha parameter that controls the degree of detail. Balangé et al [9] suggested a convex hull for a limited number of points and a B-spline based approach for the envelope of a more complex cross-section. As the B-spline approach reduces usage for further analysis, a segmented convex hull approach is used in this paper to evaluate a cross-sectional area at a point selected for analysis.

While an exact match between the simulation points and an experimentally determined point cloud cannot be guaranteed, a point cluster is initially extracted using a cylindrical search volume defined by a start and endpoint and a radius. These points are then projected onto a plane with two-dimensional coordinate system defined by a rotation of the global coordinate system with the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization, so that the new x-axis matches the cylinder axis. The origin of this projection coordinate system is defined as the first point. The vertical axis is the rotated z-axis (coordinates defined as v) and the horizontal axis is defined as the inverted rotated y-axis (coordinates defined as h).

To calculate the cross-sectional envelope, the centroid (v_c, h_c) of the projected points is calculated and used as center for a segmentation of the points into a user-defined number of subsections defined by their angular range. For each subsection an individual convex hull is calculated and all hulls are then combined to a single hull curve, where duplicate points are removed and the area of the subsegments hulls are added up to calculate the area of the combined cross-section.

To define the segments based on angular values, Eq. 5 is used to calculate the angle of each projected point with coordinates (v_i, h_i) relative to the centroid and additionally converted in a value range of $[0, 2\pi]$.

$$\theta_i = \text{atan}^2(h_i - h_c, v_i - v_c) \quad (5)$$

Starting from the first segment (with lower boundary $\theta = 0$) the points in this segment are extracted on the border angle θ_{start} and θ_{end} of this segment and a convex hull is calculated for the points. In addition to the number of sections the shape of each segment hull and thus the accuracy of the approach is highly depending on the point of the transition boundary between the sections. In the absence of a point on the boundary, an artificial point must be created to prevent an indentation between two segments, which could significantly impact the results. A search area with a defined threshold is used to identify a point with the maximal distance to the centroid point in each of the neighbouring sections of a border. If no point is found in a section, the threshold is iteratively increased with a threshold delta until a maximum number of iterations is reached. To define the distance of this boundary point to the centroid, the mean value of both distances in the neighbouring segments are used. If the maximum distance of the current segment is more than 1.5 times smaller than that of the adjacent segment, this smaller value is used. This avoids an overprediction of the segments hull, if a small sized segment is neighbouring a larger one.

Since the usability of the approach depends on the density of the point distribution, two approaches are used to identify the border points. For a high-density distribution, a rectangular shaped search area with the angular boundary line as center line is applied. Points with the greatest distance from the centroid can be effectively identified, even when the distribution follows a grid-like configuration as it can occur with the previous mentioned approach. As the threshold and the delta of the iteration needs to be as low as possible to avoid an overprediction of the hulls, the rectangular approach is more time consuming for a low point distribution. With an angular based and thus circular search area, the coverage expands proportionally with increasing distance from the centroid. While the search area can be rapidly expanded, the likelihood of selecting suboptimal points increases in the presence of large spatial

discontinuities within the search region. The centroid and the calculated points on the boundary line are then added to the point cloud of the segment. An individual convex hull is calculated for the subsection, where the segment area A_{seg} of the segments convex hull polygon can be calculated according to Bronstein et al. [10] with Eq. 6.

$$A_{seg} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^n (h_j v_{j+1} - h_{j+1} v_j) \quad (6)$$

The result for the segment area and the convex hull points without the centroid can then be added to data defining the full hull envelope. This procedure is executed in an anti-clockwise direction until the initial segment reached, completing the loop. If during calculation a segment is reached that contains less than the required three points to calculate a convex hull its angular range is merged with the next segment. Fig. 4 shows a comparison of a convex hull (Fig. 4 a)) to the segmented hull approach with a low segment number of 12 (Fig. 4 b)) and the respective boundary points. With the convex hull the shape and area of 156.8 mm^2 are overpredicted, whereas the segmented approach results in a better prediction with an area of 138.6 mm^2 . Increasing the number of segments to 360 further improves the accuracy of the calculation to an area of 134.2 mm^2 . To avoid artifacts and indentations resulting from isolated internal points, the threshold parameter needs to be increased to ensure that smaller segments are integrated into larger ones.

Figure 4: a) Projected points with a hull border resulting out of convex hull that is overpredicting the shape of specimen cross-section. b) Hull using the segmented approach with a low number of 12 segments enabling a more precise calculation of the envelope curve.

Analogous to the method proposed by Jones, the fiber volume ratio of the calculated cross-section can be estimated by dividing the amount n_{Fil} of physical filaments d_{fiber} within the cross-section by the summed area A_{Env} of the hull envelope curve representing the deformed cross-sectional boundary, as defined in Equation 7.

$$FVR = p_d \frac{n_{Fil} \cdot \pi \cdot \left(\frac{d_{fiber}}{2}\right)^2}{A_{Env}} \quad (7)$$

Since the cross-sectional area alone is insufficient to fully characterize the shape or quantify deviation, additional geometric parameters are required. In this paper, the moments of inertia I_{hh} , I_{vv} and I_{hv} in the two-dimensional coordinate system are used. As the points that define the envelope of the hull curve is a closed polynomial with already anti-clockwise sorted points, a mathematical approach by Steger [11] based on the Gaussian trapezoidal formula is used (Eq. 8 to 11).

$$I_{hh} = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (v_i^2 + v_i v_{i+1} + v_{i+1}^2) \cdot a_i \quad (8)$$

$$I_{vv} = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (h_i^2 + h_i h_{i+1} + h_{i+1}^2) \cdot a_i \quad (9)$$

$$I_{hv} = -\frac{1}{24} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} (h_i v_{i+1} + 2h_i v_i + 2h_{i+1} v_{i+1} + h_{i+1} v_i) \cdot a_i \quad (10)$$

$$a_i = h_i v_{i+1} - h_{i+1} v_i \quad (11)$$

As an alternative approach, the maximal dimension $d_{\max,h}$ in horizontal and $d_{\max,v}$ in vertical direction in the cross-sections coordinate system are calculated for the hull points of the cross-section according to Eq. 12 and 13.

$$d_{\max,h} = h_{\max} - v_{\min} \quad (12)$$

$$d_{\max,v} = v_{\max} - v_{\min} \quad (13)$$

This approach enables fast and, in most cases, a stable estimation of irregular cross-sectional areas without requirement for iterations. However, local variations in the computed area may arise due to the choice of the number of segments and the method used to determine points along the boundary between segments, as well as the corresponding threshold value. As the centroid of all points is used as the center for the circular segmentation, concave regions with slender overhangs encompassing multiple circular segments simultaneously, or cross-sections with a predominantly rectangular geometry cannot be accurately represented using this method. To address such cases and use more circular input data for the approach, an additional grid-based subdivision before the aforementioned approach needs to be implemented. This requires an additional consideration of the additional grid boundaries and sorting of edge points along the outer hull curve.

2.3 OPTIMIZATION APPROACH

The framework for the scripted implementation of the optimization problem of parameter identification for the expansion process is based on a LS-Opt workflow. The software is a multiparameter, multi-objective optimization platform for highly user specific approaches. Although it was originally created for LS-Dyna it supports any scriptable software and FE-solver. The flowchart in Fig. 6 shows the optimization strategy and workflow.

A successive response surface method was utilized for the optimization problem. In this approach, the solver selects D-Optimal points from the initial design space, evaluates the corresponding responses, and constructs a polynomial metamodel to estimate optimal design points. These design points are used to generate a solver input file for the SimTex simulation via an implementation of the methods in subsection 2.1 in a Python script. The results of each simulation are then post-processed using BetaCAE Meta, a software tool tightly integrated into LS-OPT, providing a user-friendly Python interface for post-processing. To address the challenges posed by highly nonlinear response surfaces, sequential domain reduction is employed. This technique refines the design space iteratively, improving convergence towards optimal solutions. For the expansion simulation the following parameters were identified as influential and were included in the optimization process.

Percentage strain via fiber modulus and internal loading: A combination of the Young's modulus of the fiber and internal contraction loading applies a direct nodal load. This induces up to 0.25 % elastic strain, acting effectively as a global tensile force. With increased nodal loading, the force equilibrium shifts toward a more compact cross-sectional configuration.

Fiber volume ratio: This parameter scales the combined surface area of virtual fibers and affects the cross-sectional area of bar elements during preprocessing.

Figure 5: Flowchart of the optimization workflow.

Contact stiffness between fibers: It determines the degree of overlap at contact areas between fibers, particularly at termination time or converged nodal force equilibrium. This parameter scales and balances the cross-sectional area for locations of different interacting nodal forces.

Contact properties: This includes parameters such as contact thickness and penalty stiffness. These values are crucial for defining realistic interactions and avoid interpenetrations.

Friction parameters for fiber-fiber and sleeve-fiber interaction: The friction affects the deformation behavior and shape of fiber cross sections under tension by influencing sliding and sticking between contact surfaces.

Fiber density: The density of the fibers acts as a mass scaling factor to adjust the time step size and maintain contact stability, especially for the sleeve regions with high tension and contact forces. This compensates for current limitations in the SimTex solver's capabilities.

Simulation time: The simulation time is set as a fixed parameter for all simulations. Kinetic energy convergence is not used as a termination criterion, as local fiber movements introduce oscillations that reduce numerical performance without significantly enhancing accuracy. As a result, the optimized parameter sets are only representative for the selected simulation run time.

Furthermore, the accuracy of the optimization, regarding cross-sectional shapes and the position of their center of gravity highly depends on an accurate base model. The primary goal is to derive realistic approximations of cross sections to support subsequent structural analyses. The target function used for optimization is the mean square root error calculated from a set of identifying metrics for multiple cross sections. The selected cross sections represent key structural interaction mechanisms: the interaction between sleeve and fiber, the interaction between mostly parallel fibers and at the intersection points of multiple crossing tows.

Each cross section with additional points added to discretize the contact area during analysis is characterized by its surface area and the maximum extents $d_{\max,h}$ and $d_{\max,v}$ (Eq. 12 and 13) within the projection plane. These geometric descriptors are sufficient for identifying and comparing structural responses across design variants. While more detailed metrics, such as moments of inertia (Eq. 8 to 1), can be more descriptive especially for subsequent evaluation of mechanical performance. Specifically, these values inherently scale with the square of the distance from a reference point, which must itself be accurately defined and matched between datasets. This dependency adds numerical weighting that can reduce the convergence rate of the optimization algorithm by overemphasizing deviations in geometry relative to location. Consistency in cross section analysis between reference and simulation data is achieved by using identical extraction methods respectively. This alignment ensures that the evaluated parameters reflect true physical variations rather than differences arising from analysis methodology.

3 EXPERIMENTAL DATA GENERATION

In order to validate simulation results, different sizes of robotically wound specimen are used. The basis for the optimization of parameters is a small model with two anchors of 200 mm distance and an

intersection of the fibers in the middle of the anchors. For an evaluation of the approach a middle-sized model with four anchors and a dimension of $320\text{ mm} \times 160\text{ mm}$ is used. Both of the specimen consist of a fiber bundle out of two fibers of type Teijin Carbon Tenax-E STS40 F13 48K with a filament diameter of 0.007 mm . The fibers are impregnated with the resin MGS LR 135 and the curing agent combination MGS LH 138 / LH287 with a fiber volume ratio of 40 %. The structures were impregnated in an inline impregnation process within the winding head, so that the influence of different resin viscosities is negligible. For both specimen, six layers of fibers are used, resulting in a total number of 12 fiber bundles at fiber intersection points. The specimens were scanned with a terrestrial laser scanner (TLS) of type Trimble X7 with a 3D Point accuracy of 2.4 mm at a distance of 10 m . A target-based registration and a Statistical Outlier Removal (SOR) filter in CloudCompare was applied to the data to remove isolated points. To increase the point density for evaluation, especially during the optimization approach, the specimen were additionally scanned with a structured light 3D scanning (ATOS III Rev. 02 800) with a measurement volume of $560\text{ mm} \times 420\text{ mm} \times 420\text{ mm}$ (CP40/MV560) with a measuring point distance of 0.176 mm . Target points on the specimen mounting device and scanning spray was used during the measurements. The data was processed, referenced and cropped with the associated manufacturer software GOM Inspect. As the specimen do consist of an irregular and curved surface, three tilting angles of the sample holder and multiple repositions around the rotation axis were used for a high coverage ratio during this scanning. Nevertheless, areas around the sleeve and in the area between sleeve and intersection point in the middle of the structure cannot be fully captured using this approach. However, a comparison of the two measurement methods in Fig. 6 b) shows a more precise capturing of the specimen for the structured light scanning. The measured points of the TLS are more distributed, but a scanning of large structures in a short time as a higher field of view is available and fewer scanning positions are required. As the sleeve positions were taught manually during production, a deviation of the sleeve positions measured in the teach-in and the specimen mounting devices in the lower millimetre range cannot be avoided. In order to use the scanned data for a comparison between experiment and simulation, the sleeve positions were manually adjusted to the point clouds in CloudCompare.

Figure 6: a) Result of the winding process for the small specimen used for optimization. b) Comparison of scanning results: The TLS measuring points (red) are more distributed compared to the structured light 3D scan, but enable a measurement of larger structures.

4 RESULTS

The discrete simulation effects and respective displacements are shown in Fig. 7. The initial virtual tow with overlapping elements (Fig. 7 a)) is expanding due to contact (Fig. 7 b)) without internal loading with limited displacements. With a global tension force, applied as internal loading, without fiber-fiber friction a high level of compaction of the tow can be achieved (Fig. 7 c)). The fiber deformation is significantly influenced by the parameter set used and the results are depending on time of evaluation. It should be noted that numerical optimization approaches furthermore always directly depend on a representative model, and accurate results extraction. The simulation results are evaluated after a runtime of 2.25 s with an increased stabilizing damping factor of 0.4 during the first second of the simulation.

After this a damping value of 0.05 is used. A cross-section (Fig. 7 d)) at the intersection in the middle of the specimen (point 1) and at one fiber strand (point 2) are used for optimization. The optimized results for 32 fibers model provide a parameter set of inputs (Table 1) that show good accuracy for deviation of area ($< 5.5\%$ for point 1 and $< 1\%$ for point 2) and maximal dimensions simultaneously (vertical and horizontal deviation $< 10.0\%$ for point 1 and $< 13.0\%$ for point 2). A usage of 16 fibers increases the area deviation for point 1 and dimension deviation for point 2 by 1.5%. However, the moments of inertia are overestimated by up to 30%.

Figure 7: Discrete simulation effects and displacements: a) Initial model setup. b) Expansion of filaments due to contact resolution without fiber-fiber friction. c) Applied global tension force as internal loading. d) Optimization reference points and respective cross-sections.

The optimized parameter set for the non-physical digital element simulation shows that FVR is comparable to target values during manufacturing and that the scale factor (s) for the cross-section matches initial suggestions. The friction values for fiber-fiber friction μ_{FF} are nearly identical for both numbers of virtual fibers, with a slightly increased value for 16 fibers virtual to endure the shape of the expanding cross-section. The fiber stiffness E_{Fiber} and density ρ_{fiber} are adjusted to enable a fast computation as anticipated during a digital element simulation, but still enable an enhanced dynamic response and stiffness of the fibers during the simulation. The penalty stiffness for the sleeve-fiber contact $E_{Penalty_{SF}}$ is higher than that of the inter-fiber contacts $E_{Penalty_{FF}}$ to reduce interpenetrations at the sleeve. A sleeve thickness h_{sleeve} of 2.0 mm is additionally prescribed to meet this requirement. The optimized value for the number of virtual fibers indicates that a relatively small number of virtual fibers is sufficient for a low aerial deviation, which is also advantageous for larger structures.

Parameter	Description		Optimum for 16 fibers	Optimum for 32 fibers
FVR	Fiber Volume Ratio	–	0.38	0.38
n_{virt_fibers}	Number of virtual fibers	–	16	32
l_{fiber}	Length of fiber element	[mm]	2.0	2.0
h_{sleeve}	Thickness of sleeve	[mm]	2.0	2.0
s	Scale factor	–	0.53	0.53
μ_{FF}	Inter-Fiber friction	–	0.11	0.08
μ_{SF}	Sleeve-Fiber friction	–	0.26	0.26
$E_{Penalty_{FF}}$	Inter-Fiber penalty stiffness	[MPa]	1197.59	1225.7
$E_{Penalty_{SF}}$	Sleeve-Fiber penalty stiffness	[MPa]	15000.00	15000.00
E_{fiber}	Young's modulus of fiber	[MPa]	96857.0	98279.4
E_{sleeve}	Young's modulus of sleeve	[MPa]	50000.0	50000.0
ρ_{fiber}	Density of fiber	$\left[\frac{t}{mm^3}\right]$	0.01	0.01
ρ_{sleeve}	Density of sleeve	$\left[\frac{t}{mm^3}\right]$	0.5	0.5
IL_{fiber}	Fiber internal loading	[N]	-0.1	-0.1

Table 1: Optimized values for 16 and 32 virtual fibers.

To examine the transferability of the optimized parameters to larger structures, the methodology and the optimized values for 16 fibers were evaluated for a model with four sleeves. In Fig. 9 the respective results of geometry and a cross-section (A-B) for process simulation (Fig. 9 a)), multifilament approach (Fig. 9 b)) and scanned data (Fig. 9 c)) are shown. As the process simulation uses a two-dimensional modeling approach the volume defined by the contact is replicated with artificial nodes. The results show, that the cross-sectional shape at the intersection point in the middle of the structure (A-B) cannot be fully captured using this approach. In addition, the clustered distribution of the virtual fibers implies an insufficient influence of the internal contraction force so that the initial distance of the fiber path out of the process simulation cannot be compensated. Since such a clustering of the elements limits the application of the segmented hull, an evaluation is carried out with a single segment as a normal convex hull. The calculated area of 266.0 mm^2 for the multifilament approaches has a smaller deviation to the scan data (187.7 mm^2) compared to the initial result of the process simulation (316.8 mm^2). The vertical dimension is overestimated by 20 % and the horizontal dimension by 39 % resulting in a large deviation in the moment of inertia. Nevertheless, the multifilament approach shows comparable fiber alignment to the scan data at the fiber junction area at the sleeves (Fig. 9, blue frame). In addition to a longer simulation duration that may cause penetrations at the sleeves, additional consideration of the internal loading as an optimization parameter and a reduction of the yarn geometry of the process simulation could reduce the deviations.

Figure 9: Comparison of modeling and simulation models and a respective cross-section showing convex hull and principal moments of inertia (A-B): a) Simulation result of the process simulation and respective point cloud to replicate the contact volume. b) Result multifilament approach using optimized values for 16 fibers. c) Scanned structure with additional (unscanned) sleeve geometry.

5 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

The presented work employs a multifilament and parameter optimization approach in the solver SimTex to improve the prediction of final fiber architecture and enables the simulation of complex bundle deformations during the coreless winding process. The paper describes relations between design variables and respective interactions and provides an optimized parameter set that is showing good accuracy in area estimation to a real-world equivalent used during optimization. It showed that a relative low number of filaments can be sufficient for a reasonable prediction of a cross-sectional area, thus reducing the computational expenditure. However, to enhance the stability of the optimization, the area has a greater influence than the maximal dimensions of a cross-section. As the shape is not considered

sufficiently this further reduces a transferability of the optimized parameter results to a larger structure. In further optimizations, an equal weighting of the parameters should be considered to improve the predictive capabilities for the shape of a cross-section. Furthermore, a more representative basis model should be used and interrelations of fiber bundle modelling during process simulation and multifilament simulation results need to be studied to improve the transferability to more complex simulation models.

In a continuation of the work, the proposed simulation chain can be used to generate discretised geometrical data for a simplified but fast beam model. Using the local center of mass and moments of inertia, the mechanical behaviour of a structure could be predicted with reasonable accuracy. A complete simulation chain can thus be used to virtually validate or optimize a structural design on a high detail level.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The present work is supported by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under Germany's Excellence Strategy – EXC 2120/1 – 390831618.

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